

Governance Mechanisms for Federated Digital Platform Ecosystems

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Abstract. This paper defines governance factors and mechanisms for complex, federated digital platform ecosystems, characterized by a variety of interaction models among various stakeholders that have different motivations and incentives to participate in an ecosystem. The proposed governance framework is compared with the recent research in platform ecosystem governance design, and further structured into five areas to allow for a coherent policy acquisition and modelling across the platform consortium. The proposed governance framework addresses both data- and service-driven policy mechanisms, including emerging mechanisms caused by the recent changes of public policies created to balance ethical frameworks of platform companies, transparency reporting, fairness and algorithm transparency, responsibility, etc. Furthermore, a holistic federated governance architecture to be implemented for the enforcement of major governance mechanisms is presented in the paper. The motivation to explore the governance mechanisms for federated digital platform ecosystems, relates to the design and implementation of an innovative, federated industrial platform ecosystem currently developed in the European H2020 Research and Innovation Programme.

Keywords: Governance, Federated Digital Platforms, Platform Ecosystem.

1 Motivation

This paper discusses how emerging multi-sided digital platform ecosystems should be governed to reach their goals and create sustainable outcomes. The governance mechanisms for digital platform ecosystems need to reflect the lawful interactions of key stakeholders, be they owners of the platforms, companies using the platform, or developers, users, advertisers, economists, computer scientists, governments or regulators. The interests and legal roles require a balanced interplay and understanding of interdependencies between all collaborating sides in such an ecosystem. In addition, the complexity of digital platform ecosystem governance mechanisms relates to a variety of services, applications, devices, network, data and data sources as technology enablers of various interaction models.

To reduce risks and vulnerabilities in the collaborative relationship, trust and information sharing have been reported as strongly correlated in recent research, e.g. from dyadic data analysis [1,2,3,4,5] to multi-sided platforms [6,7]. To stimulate positive

interaction payoffs within the platform ecosystem, both platform stakeholders and platform technology enablers need to be regulated and governed. Governance challenges come in many forms and through various questions; for example, how to setup membership; who makes decisions about the product, network, technology support, etc.; who maintains the platform instances; how are new services implemented and deployed; who owns the Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs); and more. One of the greatest challenges is how to get business competitors to cooperate within the platform ecosystems. Here, different efficiency gains, Return of Investments (ROIs) and other incentives through ecosystems need to be supported by the right governance mechanisms.

Our motivation to explore governance mechanisms for federated digital platform ecosystems comes from the design and deployment of a collaborative manufacturing platform ecosystem of four heterogeneous, cloud-based manufacturing platforms, currently being developed in a European innovation project called eFactory [8]. The eFactory platform interlinks four base platforms developed since 2016 (i.e. NIMBLE¹, COMPOSITION², DIGICOR³, and vf-OS⁴), and funded by the European Commission as part of the “Factories of the Future” programme within Horizon 2020.

Paper organization. Section 1 explained our motivation to research the federated governance mechanisms for emerging digital platform ecosystems. Section 2 explores the literature, relevant definitions and design principles of governance mechanisms. Section 3 explores emerging governance concepts such as self-governance, external governance and co-governance that have been presented in [10]. Section 4 introduces federated governance mechanisms to be designed and enforced through the eFactory platform ecosystem. Here, we present the architecture of the eFactory Governance Framework as a basis for policy collection, modelling and enforcement. Section 5 contains concluding remarks and provides proposals for future research.

2 Literature Review on Governance Mechanisms for Digital Platform Ecosystems

The ongoing digital transformations are rapidly changing digital platform business models from two- and multi-sided (matchmakers) platform businesses to platform-enabled multi-industry ecosystems. Digital platforms are seen as *a type of modular artefacts designed for collaboration and innovation between multiple entities, to leverage the economics of scope* [9]. The authors in [42] distinct among three categories of digital platforms: (i) *internal platforms*, enabling internal performances within the firm, (ii) *supply chain platforms*, supporting external business within the supply chain, and (iii) *industry platforms*, for the use by multiple industries and actors. The focus of this paper is on digital platform ecosystems and thus, the review covers specifically governance mechanisms for digital platform ecosystems. The authors in [10] provides a systematic literature review of 48 articles published in the period between 2010 and

¹ <https://www.nimble-project.org/>

² <https://www.composition-project.eu/>

³ <https://www.digicor-project.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.vf-os.eu/>

2017, analysing governance and control aspects of digital platform ecosystems, while excluding internal and supply chain platforms. The same authors in [10] summarize the present state of research in this area and emphasize a variety of reasons why the existing research on platform's governance mechanisms cannot be directly applied to platform ecosystems:

- Most existing governance studies are focused on single firms or projects [11],
- The results from a software platform development context are focused on the principal-agent relationship, which cannot be found in platform ecosystems [12,13],
- The absence of contractual or hierarchical relationships and controls between ecosystem leaders and other participating organizations [14],
- The number of actors in an ecosystem requires a more cost-effective governance mechanism [15],
- The actors in a platform ecosystem have a different lifecycle, e.g. industrial infrastructure providers have a lifecycle of 15-20 years, while industrial services have a shorter lifecycle, which increases the complexity of coordination of their collaboration [9].

Several definitions of a digital platform ecosystems emphasize a specific organization of an ecosystem (i.e. a set of firms and various actors) around digital multi-sided platforms [6,7], and involving multiple platform leaders and a large number of relevant complementors which show their collaborating and competitive nature and a high level of interdependencies towards a shared vision on the prosperity of the platform [16,17].

The review on platform governance design methods identified various approaches; for example: Tiwana et al. in [12] describe the following three aspects of governance design: decision rights, control and ownership; Mukhopadhyay and Bouwman in [10] emphasize the role of the following five aspects of governance design:

- *ecosystem design* – based on the following four dimensions: leadership structure (e.g. a single platform leader or multiple leaders jointly creating a platform [18]); membership openness (e.g. closed, open or controlled access mechanism); tiering structure (i.e. different levels of membership can reduce coordination complexity [19] and motivates complementors to make a higher contribution [20]); and decision rights sharing (e.g. a decentralized decision making increases trust among platform participants, leverages complementor's knowledge of a specific domain and enhances the perceived fairness and credibility of the decision process [21]).
- *ecosystem coordination mechanisms* - based on shared values, and implicit or explicit rules for value exchange [22]. Some examples of coordination mechanisms include: self-regulations, which appeared to be more effective than formal controls [13,14]; “governance at arm's length” that suggests a standardized ecosystem coordination [15], or “dyadic governance” for collaborating with important complementors [15, 23].
- *ecosystem value co-creation* – based on: effective complementary resource integration; increased interaction among the partners; proper definition of the roles in the ecosystem [22]; increased application market competition to boost the variety of outputs; exclusive agreement with key complementors; leveraging boundary resources (Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), Software Development Kits (SDK), technical documentation) to prevent application development that is not compatible with the vision of the platform leaders [24].

- *ecosystem value appropriation* – based on transparent/ fair revenue sharing which positively impacts complementors' intention to stay with the platform ecosystem [25], risks mitigation, building reputation mechanisms [21, 12, 19, 24].
- *ecosystem architectural principles* – based on the degree of modularity, openness and richness of interfaces.

In addition to the review of governance design methods for digital platform ecosystems, we explore the following IT governance frameworks:

- *ITIL (Information Technology Infrastructure Library) framework* for IT service management and delivery. It provides guidance on how IT processes should be planned, designed and implemented to serve the needs of business. According to [28,29], majority of ITIL processes remain applicable for the provisioning of IT services through Cloud Computing (CC).
- *ISO/IEC 38500 or COBIT 5.0 (Control Objectives for Information and Related Technologies) governance framework*, published by the Information Systems Audit and Control Association (ISACA). COBIT is an IT governance framework and toolset that allows managers to bridge the gap between control requirements, technical issues and business risks [26]. COBIT is also developed to provide control and governance strategy around CC governance challenges, CC infrastructures and services [30,31].
- *ISO/IEC 27001/2 standard* with a focus on implementation of an Information Security Management System (ISMS) for designing and implementing a coherent set of information security controls.
- *Cloud Computing (CC) governance model* that identifies the following four key governance domains in the cloud: Cloud Migration (CM) with the required controls for planning, executing, evaluating, and monitoring CC migration; Information Security (IS) with the required controls for CC security measures; Risk Management (RM) with the controls for identification, analysis, mitigation, monitoring and review of CC security risks; and Service Level Agreement (SLA) with the controls for initiation, negotiation, establishment, monitoring, enforcement and termination of CC SLAs [27]. The CC governance framework provides an independent approach based on the above three governance models.

The information/data governance has received little attention in platform ecosystem research [32]. The authors in [33] identify gaps of existing governance frameworks for platform ecosystems and highlight the following nineteen data governance factors that should be considered when implementing data governance:

- P1. Define data ownership of all types of data in the platform (e.g. user, process and system data);
- P2. Define access rights based on the ownership and contribution of a data contributor;
- P3. Identify main criteria for defining data ownership;
- P4. Consider relevant regulations (laws, standards and cases);
- P5. Develop decision models for defining of data owners/access;
- P6. Consider contributor's efforts for value creation;
- P7. Identify dimensions for a measurement model
- P8. Combine contribution with data ownership/access definition model;

- P9. Define data categories of a platform including various sources (e.g. user, process and system data);
- P10. Define data use cases and individual use case, based on the data categories;
- P11. Keep consistency and integrity of the use cases;
- P12. Recognize requirements for data due processes;
- P13. Define audit process for conformance of the due processes;
- P14. Consider the result of audit make visible to stakeholders;
- P15. Detect and notify all activities regarding the use of the data in the platform;
- P16. Allow all participating groups to monitor and report the use of the data;
- P17. Achieve visibility of the data supply chain to stakeholders;
- P18. Trace all the derivation history of the data through metadata management;
- P19. Facilitate data owner authentication through data lifecycle.

3 Emerging Governance Mechanisms

Currently emerging platform governance models can be classified as following one of these three basic models: self-governance, external governance and co-governance [10]. In this section, we briefly look at the major features of each of these emerging models, before defining federated governance mechanisms based on the eFactory case.

- *Self-Governance Mechanisms*: The self-governance or self-regulation model is currently the most dominant governance model. It allows a *laissez-faire* relationship between governing institutions and platform companies. In this model, the platform decisions are made with minimal external oversight [34]. We note that this is slowly changing and in the past two years, platforms are beginning to increase transparency in numerous areas, e.g. content policy and political advertising [10]. One of the major advantages of the self-governance model is that it allows companies to quickly make interventions, long before legislation comes into effect. Some important limitations are that voluntary arrangements rely on goodwill and provide e.g. useful tools for journalists, but much less useful information for regulators.
- *External Governance Mechanisms*: The external governance model appears either in a form of legislation around existing policy levers or legislations that affect the business models and practices of certain companies and industries. For example: the German Network Enforcement (NetzDG) law removes liability protections for content violating German law [35]. Another example is the European Union's 2018 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) that gives clear requirements to the platforms on how to process personal data and introduces penalties for non-compliance [36].
- *Co-Governance Mechanisms*: This model seeks to provide values of democratic accountability without making extreme changes to the current platforms [10]. It is about the ways to support platform cooperatives, decentralized systems, and other various forms of community self-management. It investigates multiple platform functionalities, e.g. user complaints, ethical frameworks for platform companies, transparency reporting, third party audits, fairness, accountability, responsibility, etc. [37].

4 Federated Governance Mechanisms for Platform Ecosystem

Our motivation in this paper is to find the best governance model for a federation of interoperating digital platforms, in order to overcome the complexity of decision making among different actors in the platform ecosystem and different solution providers. The decision making layers include platform owners, platform technology support, users, legal, regulatory, marketing and other business model decisions. Figure 1 illustrates the scope of governance mechanisms in eFactory ecosystem, e.g. software development governance is addressed by using the architecture/IT governance mechanisms; data governance addresses the decisions related to the data as defined by nineteen data governance factors given in [33]; etc. The following is a list of regulations of interest for the platform ecosystem: EU Network and Information Security (NIS) Directive [38], national cybersecurity strategies [39], Technical Guidelines for the implementation of minimum security measures for Digital Service Providers (DSPs) by ENISA [40], incident notification for DSPs in the context of the NIS Directive by ENISA [41], GDPR, ISO/IEC NP 24392, Information technology --- Security techniques – Security reference model for Industrial Internet Platform (IIP), Ethical Trading Initiative (ETI) for addressing business ethics, etc.

For the sake of structuring platform ecosystem governance elements from Figure 1, we further map these elements to the five aspects of governance design presented in [10]. Figure 2 illustrates mapping details for more complete governance design in eFactory, e.g. mapping of “Ecosystem Design” from [10] to *Terms & Conditions* and *Privacy Policies* in eFactory; “Ecosystem Architectural Principles” from [10] are mapped to *Architecture/IT* policies of eFactory; “Ecosystem Value Co-Creation” from [10] is mapped to *Data* and *Service* policies in eFactory; etc.

Fig. 1. The scope of digital platform ecosystem governance elements in eFactory.

The eFactory Governance Framework (GF) is holistic by its nature, incorporating platform organizational standards, strategic planning, business rules and norms of behaviour within the ecosystem, software standards, regulatory requirements, etc. which need to be continuously monitored and assessed.

Fig. 2. Mapping of the five aspects of governance design from [10] to the eFactory Governance Framework.

Figure 3 illustrates the high-level architecture of the eFactory GF. Apart from continuous platform monitoring and assessment, the framework includes Roles and Responsibilities, Governance Registry and Governance Decisions and Feedback services. Some examples of roles and responsibilities are: Governance Manager (defines the roles and responsibilities; defines business process lifecycle; monitor services, etc.), Business Process Designer (defines business process choreography policies and choreography level agreements), Service Provider, etc.

Fig. 3. High-level architecture of the eFactory Governance Framework.

Depending on user's roles in the platform ecosystem, to create the best governance decisions and feedback, users set priorities and focus using the Governance Registry. In addition, the Governance Manager sets a variety of policies in the system, including rating and ranking policies, which are later used for calculating trust and reputation in the platform ecosystem. Furthermore, the access management in eFactory is based on the User Managed Access (UMA 2.0) protocol, which is an authorisation framework defined on top of OAuth 2.0.

5 Conclusion and Next Steps

This paper has presented salient federated governance mechanisms that we are currently implementing in eFactory. Our governance framework is aligned with recent research on platform ecosystem governance design. It also considers the Cloud Computing (CC) governance framework with an emphasis on information security and risk management, both of which are incorporated in the proposed architecture of the eFactory GF. The architecture allows for coherent collection, modelling and enforcement of a variety of policies in the ecosystem.

A further important aspect of governance in loosely federated platform ecosystems is finding the balance between complementarity of services and “parasitic collaboration” e.g. when competitors make use of the ecosystem's available services to extend their own service offering, without sufficient compensation towards the ecosystem partners from which those services originate. This requires a sophisticated quantitative and qualitative accounting system across the ecosystem. Other directions for future work include exploring (i) autonomous governance mechanisms for selecting the best rules fairly, by combining game theory, blockchain technology, Adversarial Machine Learning (AML) to reduce the cybersecurity attack surface within the platform ecosystem and (ii) economic incentives to attract the participation of platform ecosystem businesses.

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